

Career Advancement And Employees Productivity: A Study Of Selected Hotels In Lagos State, Nigeria

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Abstract: Career advancement in organisations is one of the key enablers of employees' productivity and it has a dual positive impact on both individual employees and the organisation. It enables the employees to enhance their skills, increase and sustain their earnings potential and as well improve overall job satisfaction, while also helping organizations to attract and retain talent, boost productivity, and achieve their corporate goals. Globally, employees are regarded as major assets and components which all forward looking organisations will not toy with because their collective performance or non-performance ultimately determines the fortunes of the organisation. The reward system of organisations is seen as one of the most effective strategies which organisations use to retain top performing employees and maintains a motivated workforce to sustain productivity. This study aims to highlight the impact of career advancement of employees as it affects their productivity on their job.

Survey research design were employed where 150 copies of the research instruments were administered to purposively selected respondents who were senior, middle level and lower management employees of the selected hotels. The effective follow up on the distributed copies of the questionnaire ensured that we achieved a response rate 124 copies representing 82.66% of the instruments distributed. The data were processed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

The study found that career advancement had a significant effect on employee productivity of selected hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\beta = 0.501$, $t = 8.271$, $p < 0.05$).

The study concluded that career advancement played a significant role in employee productivity of selected hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria. The study therefore recommended that organisations should institute robust employee career advancement management in their compensation packages so that they will be able to recruit, train and retain talented employees in order to improve and sustain individual employee performance as well as overall organisational productivity.

Keywords: Career advancement, Employee productivity, Organisational productivity, Reward management.

1. Introduction

Employees are seen as significant assets of organisations because of their contributions to the growth and development of the establishment. Career advancement is a major policy option which many organisations adopt to reward their employees. The reward entails that the employees are treated fairly and equitably on continuous basis based on the importance and value of each employees' contribution to the organisational growth. Career advancement entails series of activities of developing employees' careers within an organisation. Such activities involve training on new skills, moving to higher job responsibilities,

making a career change within the same organization, or to a different organization or starting one's own business (MBA Skool, 2020). It is part of the overall reward management in organisations to be used in conjunction with other strategies to keep the employees motivated to increase their productivity. According to Egbuta (2019) career advancement system is a critical component of human resources that impacts both the individual and the organization, that is, both parties stand to gain. Employees would be rewarded with periodic raises in form of financial and non-financial benefits as they climb the corporate ladder while the organisation will benefit in

form of increased productivity. Career advancement also involve processes which employees strategically explore, plan, and create their future at work by designing personal learning plans to achieve their potential goals and fulfil the organization's mission requirements (Omair, 2010). Khan, Rajasekar, and Al-Asfour (2015) were of the view that most organizations often use career advancement programmes to assist their employees to plan their careers properly early in life because it is believed that, generally employees react positively to career advancement opportunities to improve their well-being and profile. Thus, the career advancement processes are usually a joint effort between the individual employee and the organization.

Organizations establish different plans for their employees because they play vital roles in building commitment which results to retention of employees. Organisations that provides effective career advancement opportunities to their employees would most probably benefit in form of higher productivity, and this strategy could discourage employees from leaving the organization and increases loyalty rate (Kibui, Gachunga, & Namusonge, 2014). It is the desire of most employees to steadily grow with the organisation they are gainfully employed. They see organisations that could not provide or guarantee steady rise in corporate ladder as waste of valuable time that could be better utilise elsewhere. As the environment changes rapidly, employees are seeing that their individual's careers are no longer tied to a single organization, as career changes, they result to frequent job mobility that have become a common phenomenon. As postulated by Saleem, Kamran, Sabir, and Iqbal (2013) whereas in the past, employees' individual's careers somehow rested in the hands of the organizations, but in today's dynamic environment, individuals now have greater control over their own careers and may leave and search for better options if not supported to advance in their current location or job responsibilities. The lack of personal growth in organizations often results in career stagnation, ultimately resulting in increased staff attritions which would affect productivity negatively if not checked early to stem the tide. Many employees find themselves in jobs that offer them limited mobility opportunities in terms of upward movement in the organization (Simiyu & Mbithi, 2019). Kwenin (2013) stressed that when employees attained certain positions in organisation management and they perceived that the possibility of further growth would be stunted, then they could be tempted to explore exit routes from the company and seek opportunities elsewhere their chances of further growth would be enhanced. Career opportunities encourage workers to make longer-term commitments to their workplace; it permits them to see a future with the organisation where they can achieve steady grow with time.

Employee productivity can be described as employees' successful completion of tasks, assignments of projects as defined and evaluated by predefined organisation or professional standards, while effectively utilizing resources available in a changing context (Kyrgidou & Spyropoulou, 2013). The achievement of individual employees' goals and objectives are linked to employees' productivity within the office setting (Dirisu, Iyiola & Ibiidunni, 2013). Employees are regarded to be working effectively when they efficiently meet organizations established goals and objectives. Organisation performance management system according to Kyrgidou and Spyropoulou (2013), plays vital roles in improving individual performance by providing feedback, creating goals, and achieving them. It enables the employees to be objectively appraised, by highlighting both their weakness and strength areas which management will work upon to sustain overall productivity. According to Shadraconis (2013), there is a significant link between employee productivity and leadership style. Employees who believe they are appreciated and treated with respect by their employers are more likely to be better performers in their work because of their positive motivation, which leads to loyalty to their companies. According to Gavrea, Ilies, and Stegorean (2011), growing and maintaining employee performance is contingent on the organization's leadership. To achieve the organization's objective and vision, it takes a seamless combination of investment, time, commitment, and effort. Leaders must possess the necessary abilities to improve employee productivity at all times, such as involving staff in the development of shared goals, clarifying responsibilities, and delivering systematic performance evaluation (Shadraconis, 2013). Organisational leadership with transactional style often guides their followers to attain pre-determined corporate objectives based on rewards methods instituted to motivate employees. Ibrar and Khan (2015) stressed that transactional leadership style uses such rewards methods to increase the corporate performance, which are given to whom that excel in their performances. It should be known that career advancement is important to motivate employee productivity, it is not the only strategy to achieve the same objective. Adequate pay, bonuses, recognition and assigning responsibilities are some of the other variables which organisation could use to remunerate employees to achieve higher productivity. According to the results of the study conducted by Yang (2014) rewarding employees based on individual performance (whether through direct pay, bonuses or other forms of reward initiatives such as supervisory or management acknowledgement or appreciation) has a positive collection with the overall performance of an organisation.

2. Literature Review

As the organizations strive to keep abreast with the changing environment, it beholds on them to harness all its resources and potentials to enable them compete

favourably to sustain productivity. One major strategy organisations use is to motivate their employees by adequately compensating them. This they achieve through the use of financial and non-financial compensations. Career advancement is one of the sub-variable of non-financial compensation that encompasses using a range of practices designed to enhance employees' skills, knowledge, and competencies, enabling them to progress in their careers. It is imperative for organisations that operates in a highly competitive environment should institute processes to attract and retain competent employees to help the organization achieve their corporate objectives.

2.1 Career Advancement

Career advancement is seen as an organizational strategy that benefits both employees and their employers (Khan, Rajasekar, & Al-Asfour, 2015). The positive effects are felt by both parties, as it enhances individual employees' growth and also supports the organization to sustain productivity (Kaya & Ceylan, 2014). The primary aim of career advancement of employees is to enhance their abilities to meet or exceed organizational targets and fulfil customer and organizational needs. Organisations should carefully plan and structure their employees career advancement programmes through using objective and scientific methods that are able to support the company's present and future activities in line with the goals they want to achieve. When employees are rewarded through prompt promotions, it always have huge positive effects because it generally encourages hard work and healthy competitions. With a better managed career advancement programme and processes within the organization, they will be able to encourage the number of employees who have the ability to work harder because they will be rewarded in due course.

Motivation is one of the superior's tools organisations use to sustain productivity. Bosses can motivate their employees in different ways according to the mindset and preferences of each employee. As organizations strive to boost performance and productivity, career advancement has become increasingly appealing (Ojeleye, 2017). Organisations should not see investment in their human resources as a waste, rather as investments, which will positively manifest in no distant time. This is because by appropriately rewarding employees through deserved career advancement will boost productivity and also encourages hard work within the establishment. When employees acquire new skills, it will enhance their competencies, which in turn boosts their motivation and productivity at work (Nawab, & Bhatti, 2011). The study by Ogaboh., Nkpoyen and Ushie (2010) emphasized that career advancement fosters employees' commitment to the organization and this will reduce staff attrition rate. The employees will envision a future within the organization and will willingly provide

whatever support that are needed to encourage organizational growth (Wasiu & Adebajo, 2014). According to Agba, Nkpoyen, and Ushie (2010) a lack of, and or difficult career growth can make employees feel disillusioned thus increasing their desire to leave and seek better opportunities elsewhere. Additionally, carefully planned and executed career advancement programmes can significantly reduce costs associated with high turnover rates and help maintain overall staff capabilities. Regular and predictable staff promotions and advancement ultimately save the stress of new recruitments, training expenses and other associated costs which the organization would have expended when new employees are recruited. These expenses would be saved by looking inward through efficient career programmes are instituted at the organisation. This is in line with the study by Gopu, and Kaviarasu (2019) confirming that career advancement programmes enhances productivity, creativity, and long-term organizational effectiveness.

2.2 Employee Productivity

Employee productivity have been variously described as a methodology on how to efficiently and effectively assess employees' capacities to complete their tasks and contribute to organizational goals within a specific timeframe. It is a major performance indicator that measures output in relation to input, taking into consideration other variables such as time, effort, and resources. Ultimately, it relates to getting tasks done in timely fashion without compromising quality. The key elements of employees' productivity revolve around efficiency, effectiveness', output and input of resources (Ferreira & Du Plessis, 2009)

The study by Sharma and Sharma (2014) concluded that employee productivity is based on the amount of time that an employee is physically present at his/ her job, besides the extent to which he / she is mentally present or efficiently working during physical presence at the job location. Also, Ferreira and Du Plessis (2009) concluded that productivity in organisations can be measured by the amount of time an employee spends actively in carrying out organisation tasks for which they are employed, in order to achieve the desired results specified in the job description. Furthermore, higher productivity as described by Sharma and Sharma (2014) concluded that it often leads to economic growth which increased profitability leading to sustain productivity of the organisation. Employees can only get better wages/salaries, working conditions, and job possibilities if they increase their productivity. Employee productivity could also be described as the rate at which a worker in an organisation turns out goods and services, the quantity produced, with the time, money and labour used to produce them (Hornby, 2010). The rate here refers to the speed at which goods are produced or services are rendered. For a workforce to have effective productivity, there are factors that would be present, which include the need for the employees to feel that they are not just workers in the organization but being

partners' whose continued loyalty and hard work will be rewarded at a future time period (Skare, Kostelic & Jozicic, 2013).

One way of motivating employees is by giving shares and incentives. When organisations incentivise their employees, it always serves as morale booster to work hard to justify management confidence in them. They will increase their creativity levels and will develop new ideas on how to make the business grow because they now see themselves as part owners or partners of the business and organisation. Therefore, organizations should strive to satisfy the employees, customers and management, so that the organization can be more productive and grow. This can also be achieved by the organization if they utilize the capacity of their human resources for more productivity. As a result, employees will be happier and healthier, which will result to a more productive company. Studies have confirmed that the productivity level of a company's employees often determines its continuous existence and progress. Productivity is a total measure of the efficiency or capacity to transform inputs that is raw materials into finished products or services and the contribution of the human resources among the factors of production plays a vital role to achieve this transformation. George (2016) concluded that the collective performance of workers in their various capacities contributes directly or indirectly towards achieving productivity in an organization. Employees level of productivity to a large extent is dependent on the extent at which they believe that the organisations will fulfil their part of the bargain through appropriate rewards where necessary, and conversely, if the employees believe that they are being taken for a ride could openly or surreptitiously embark on actions or inactions that could harm the organization overall productivity.

2.3 Theoretical Review

The theoretical framework of this study provides an understanding of relevant theories on employees' reward management system and productivity in an organisation. The study is anchored on Equity theory and Human Capital theory. These theories explained employees' behaviours, attitudes and perceptions arising out of their compensation packages in an organisation.

2.3.1 Equity Theory by John Stacy Adams

Equity Theory was propounded by John Stacy Adams, a workplace and behavioral psychologist who developed his job motivation theory in 1963 (Anderson & Patterson, 2008). Equity theory according to Adams (1963) suggests that individuals engage in social engagement by comparing their efforts and rewards with those of their peers in similar job responsibilities within the environment. The perception of individuals about the fairness of their rewards relative to others influences their level of motivation and their decision-

making process (Duening, 2006). Equity theory came as result agitations by employees for fair and equitable treatment especially in the areas pay from their employers. Equity exists when individuals perceive that the ratio of efforts to rewards is the same for them as it is for other organisations similar to them whom they compare themselves. Inequity exists when individuals perceive that the ratio of efforts to rewards is different (usually negative) for them than it is for others to whom they compare themselves. The theory is principally divided into two parts which enable it to be evaluated especially on fairness of the situation by comparing the situation with their peers in other organisations within the same environment. According to this theory, a person (P) compares his/her own ratio of perceived outcomes (O = pay benefits, working conditions) to perceived inputs (I = effort, ability, experience, skills, training) to the ratio of a comparison other (O) – external inequity pays.

Criticisms of the theory have been directed toward its assumption. Scholars have questioned the simplicity of the model, arguing that a number of demographic, environmental and psychological variables affect people perceptions of fairness and interactions with each other. Furthermore, much of the research supporting the basic propositions of equity theory has been conducted in a controlled setting and thus has questionable applicability to real life situations (Huseman, Hatfield & Miles, 1987). According to Carrel and Dittrich (2000) in a business setting, one might feel that the applicable compensation of employees is equitable when compare with their peers within the environment which might not be true. Ng'ethe (2012) stressed that one of the major weakness of the theory is its subjectivity of the comparison processes. Beardwell and Claydon (2007) also observed that there is a tendency in human nature to distort their inputs especially in regard to effort and hence, it becomes hard when comparing their levels of commitment to the job. Another weakness of the equity theory is that a worker could be extremely dissatisfied with the work environment and seems beyond recovery to a regular, constructive state where such employee would be converted to a great asset to be utilized by the organization to promote organizational productivity.

Despite the criticism, many researchers have adopted this theory because it reveals the importance of justice, that is, equity and fairness that workers want to receive in return for rendering their services to the organisation (Akuoko, & Donkor, 2012; Laakso, 2012; Wasiu & Adebajo, 2014). The supporters of this theory advanced that the theory is beneficial to both the employees and the organization because it helps ensure employee retention, attracting talents as well as guarantees industrial peace and productivity. The theory revealed the concerns and feelings of how the employees are being treated in their current jobs in relation to their peers in similar job environment (Ng'ethe, 2012). The same author posits that employees seek to maintain equity between the inputs

they bring into a job (education, time, skills, training, experience, commitment and effort) and the outcome they receive in terms of financial and non-financial which could be promotion, higher pay and bonuses as well as recognition against the perceived inputs and outcomes of other employees in similar circumstances. Ng'ethe (2012) supported the theory and pointed out that the major strength of this theory is that, it recognizes that individual inputs such as education, experience, effort and skills should be recognized and rewarded appropriately in such a way that equity is experienced and failure to find equity would possibly leads to various actions one of which may be to leave the organization. The equity theory's other strength is related to the concept of sensitivity (Adams, Treadway & Stepina, 2008). The personal judgments of the workers directly assessed the equitable nature of the relationships in the work environment; related to their perceived treatment in the workplace by peers and management (Anderson & Patterson, 2008). Another strength of the Equity theory is that it takes time to move a worker through the three stages of the theory which are benevolent, sensitive and entitled, before the adverse results are experienced in the workplace (Jewczyn, 2010).

2.3.2 The Human Capital Theory by Theodore Schultz, Jacob Mincer and Gary Baker

The Human Capital Theory was developed in the 1960s by economists Theodore Schultz and Gary Becker and their aim was to explain the differences in employees' remunerations in organisations. The theory states that with investments and improvements in education, training, skills acquisitions by employees, it tends to increase their individual's productivity, marketability and earning potentials which contributes immensely to organisational productivity. They further argued that the theory relates to how best human resources in organisations are improved and enhanced through further education and training to increase their contributions to organisation productivity (Becker, 1962). According to the proponents of the theory, their main focus relates to aggregating the combination of competencies, knowledge, experience, social, and personal attributes embodied in the ability to create intrinsic and measurable economic value by employees to increase their earning potentials. The origin of the theory can be traced back to Adam Smith in the 18th century and the modern theory which was popularised by Gary Becker, Jacob Mincer and Theodore Schultz. The three theorists regarded human resources as economic units that could be improved upon to achieve specific organizational goals. The theorists argued that costs incurred on education and training should not be classified as expense items, but rather as investments by the organization which they will reap the benefits in no distant period (Davenport, 1996).

Human Capital theory had some assumptions which its proponents held constant. One of such assumption was the immeasurable nature of its many forms. For example, the economic capital can be measured by its ability to produce wages and salaries, however, an intrinsic value of human capital exists, although it is not always measurable or it is extremely difficult to measure (Devine & Syrett, 2014). In certain circumstances, it is possible to store human capital, but the challenge is that it will not be fully utilised sometimes which make it difficult to observe and study consistently. The literature that focuses on human capital as a measure of employee remuneration states that individual skills, level of education, age and gender, amongst other individual characteristics, account for the differences in employees' remuneration. The study by Greve, Benassi and Sti (2010) concluded that by summing up the skills and competencies of an individual, it is possible to assess his or her level of human capital and its likely contribution to organizational productivity. In the same manner, the skills and competencies of several workers can be calculated or estimate by quantifying the unit additions to overall productivity. The skills and experience that derive from accumulated education, training and skills acquired overtime is therefore an asset at both individual and organisational levels and should therefore be appropriately rewarded.

The study by Thomas, Smith and Diez (2013) concluded that human capital theory offers several advantages, including improved employee performance, higher earning potential for individuals, and a more competitive workforce for organizations. When industries and organisations achieve maximum productivity as a result of better performance from their employees, it inevitably contributes to overall economic development of the country. Also, since production levels are positively impacted, which leads to economic growth by adding to the GDP of the country. Furthermore, human capital, if prudently managed, can create distinct value for the organisation in form of increased revenue, improved customer satisfaction, enhance quality of the product and services and reduce cost. Furthermore, investing in human capital allows the organisation to see growth, measured through the employees' abilities and values acquired over a period of time and this will help increase business productivity, and in time, revenue, and brand-name.

However, despite these lofty advantages, the human capital theory is fraught with notable limitations. According to Blair (2012) some of the challenges of the theory include the difficulty in explaining income inequality, its neglect of social and cultural factors, and its tendency to oversimplify the relationship between education and productivity. Additionally, the theory's reliance on educational attainment as a proxy for human capital is problematic, as it doesn't account for skills gained through experience or informal learning. The theory's inability to explain income inequality suggests that education directly translates into higher productivity

and earnings. However, it struggles to explain why some highly educated individuals earn significantly more than others, or why income inequality has widened in many countries despite increased investment in education, skills acquisition and training. Furthermore, the theory does not adequately account for factors like social status, inherited wealth, or the role of luck in determining an individual's economic success which is a reality in certain circumstances. Also, the theory often overlooks the influence of social and cultural contexts on educational outcomes and career paths. Some crucial factors like family background, access to quality education, and societal norms could significantly impact an individual's opportunities and achievements, which were not captured by the theory. Equally important is the over simplification of education and productivity which the theory assumed has a direct and linear relationship between education and productivity, which can be overly simplistic. Becker (1962) concluded that the connection between education and workplace performance is complex and multifaceted. It should be known that skills and trainings acquired through education may not always be directly transferable to the workplace, and some jobs may require specific skills that are not necessarily acquired through formal education. The theory often uses educational

attainment (years of schooling, degrees earned) as a measure of human capital. However, this can be a flawed indicator as it doesn't capture the full range of skills and knowledge an individual possesses. Individuals may gain valuable skills and knowledge through on-the-job training, informal learning, or other experiences that are not reflected in their formal educational qualifications. Finally, while human capital theory has been a valuable framework for understanding the relationship between education and the economy, its limitations highlight the need for a more nuanced and holistic approach that considers the broader social, cultural, and institutional factors that shape individuals' lives and careers.

3. Methodology

This study used survey research design to gather information from the respondents of the selected hotels in Lagos State. The hotels are Eko Hotel limited, Golden Tulip Hotel, Presken Hotels and Resorts and Radisson Blu Hotels. The population of the study was one thousand, seven hundred and forty-two employees from the selected hotels made up senior, middle level and lower level employees of these hotels. The hotels were selected because they are top five-star hotels noted for their efficiency and comfort and have contributed immensely to the promotion of leisure and tourism in Lagos area.

Table 1.0: Population of selected Hotels

S/N	Name of Hotels	Number of Employees
1	Eko Hotel Limited	1200
2	Golden Tulip Hotel	214
3	Presken Hotels and Resorts	185
4	Radisson Blu Hotels	143
	Total	1742

Source: Lagos State Tourism Bureau

The sample size determination was derived using Taro-Yamane as follows:

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2}$$

Where: n= Sample Size

N= Population

l= Constant

e= Acceptable margin of error

Note that:

$$N= 1742; \quad \text{and} \quad e=3\% (0.09)$$

$$\text{Therefore, } n = \frac{1742}{1+1742(0.09)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{1742}{15.1102} = n = 115$$

According to the provision of Israel (2013) which discusses factors influencing sample size and provides strategies for its calculation. It also emphasizes that the appropriate sample size depends on balancing precision, confidence levels, and accounting for variability within the population. It is advisable to provide for errors in fillings, non-response rates and discrepancies that may come up as a result of questionnaire administration and retrieval. Therefore, a 30% provision will be made and added to the sample size so as to take care of such errors.

The Sample Size is given as 115

So, 30% of 115 is given as 35

Therefore $115 + 35 = 150$

4. Results and Discussions

The analysis of the response rate on the descriptive statistics is stated below:

Table 2.0: Descriptive Statistics on Career Advancement

Items	Strongly Agree	Agree	Partially Agree	Partially Disagree	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
There are regular trainings in the organizations	20.1%	41.6%	23.4%	8.6%	2.9%	3.3%	4.57	1.1830
Organizational support is made available to employees	16.3%	36.4%	27.8%	11.0%	6.7%	1.9%	4.39	1.1921
Team support is effective at different levels	24.9%	37.3%	20.6%	11.0%	4.8%	1.4%	4.62	1.1911
Initial job orientation is done for new employees	41.6%	29.2%	14.8%	7.2%	6.7%	0.5%	4.90	1.2366
Mentorship is an ongoing process in the organization	19.1%	40.2%	25.4%	8.6%	3.8%	2.9%	4.54	1.1766
Average							4.60	1.1958

Source: Researchers' Findings 2025

Table 2.0 shows the descriptive analysis on career advancement. Five items were used to get the opinions of the respondents. The table shows that 20.1% of the respondents strongly agreed to the statement that there are regular trainings in the organizations, 41.6% agreed with the statement while 23.4% partially agreed to it. Also, 8.6% partially disagreed, 2.9% of the respondents disagreed and 3.3% strongly disagreed. On average, the respondents agreed that there are regular trainings in the organizations with a mean of 4.57 and standard deviation of 1.1830. Results also indicated that 16.3% of respondents strongly agreed to the statement that organizational support is made available to employees, 36.4% of the respondents agreed, while 27.8% partially

agreed. However, about 11% of the respondent partially disagreed, 6.7% disagreed and 1.9% of the respondents strongly disagreed. On average, the respondents agreed that organizational support is made available to employees with a mean of 4.39 and standard deviation of 1.1921. When asked if team support is effective at different levels, 24.9% of the respondents strongly agreed, 37.3% agreed, 20.6% partially agreed, about 11% of the respondent partially disagreed, 4.8% disagreed and 1.4% of the respondents strongly disagreed. On average, the respondents agreed that team support is effective at different levels with a mean of 4.62 and standard deviation of 1.1911.

The study further shows that, 41.6% of the respondents strongly agreed that initial job orientation is done for new employees, 29.2% of the respondents agreed, 14.8% partially agreed, 7.2% partially disagreed, 6.7% of the respondents disagreed and 0.5% strongly disagreed. On average, the respondents agreed that initial job orientation is done for new employees with a mean of 4.90 and standard deviation of 1.2366.

Finally, 19.1% of the respondents strongly agreed to the statement that mentorship is an ongoing process in the organization, 40.2% of the respondents agreed to the statement, 25.4% of the respondents partially agreed, about 8.6% of the respondent partially disagreed, 3.8% disagreed and 2.9% of the respondents strongly disagreed. On average, the respondents partially agreed that mentorship is an ongoing process

Table 3.0: Summary of regression of the effect of Career Advancement and Employee Productivity at the selected Hotels in Lagos State.

Variables	<i>B</i>	<i>T</i>	<i>Sig</i>	<i>R</i>	<i>R</i> ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
(Constant)	13.135	9.271	.000	.498 ^a	.248	3.56375
Career advancement	.501	8.271	.000			
a. Dependent Variable: Employee productivity						

Source: SPSS output, 2025

Table 3.0 revealed that there was significant effect of career advancement on employee productivity of Selected hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria ($\beta = 0.501$, $t = 8.271$, $p < 0.05$). The $R = 0.498$ shows that there is a moderate positive relationship between career advancement and employee productivity of selected hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria. The coefficient of determination (R^2) is 0.248 shows that career advancement explains 24.8% variations in employee service quality of selected hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria while the remaining 75.2% could be attributed to other factors not included in this model. The findings revealed that the model significantly predicted employee productivity at $p < 0.05$. The regression equation from the result is given as follows:

$$ESQ = 13.135 + 0.501CA + \mu_i \dots \dots \dots \text{eq.i}$$

Where EP = Employee Productivity

CA = Career Advancement

The regression equation established that the holding other factor (career advancement) constant at zero, employee productivity will be 13.135 which means that without the influence of the predictor variable, employee productivity of selected hotels would still be 13.135 which is positive. The regression coefficient shows that Career advancement positively influences employee productivity of selected hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria. The result further shows that an improvement

in the organization with a mean of 4.54 and standard deviation of 1.1766. The grand mean of 4.60 shows that majority of the respondents agreed that career advancement has an effect on employee performance while the standard deviation of 1.1958 implies that responses were dispersed from the mean.

Hypothesis Testing

A simple linear regression analysis was used to test the hypothesis. In the analysis, career advancement is the independent variable while employee productivity is the dependent variable. The data for the variables were generated by adding responses of the items under the variables together to create index of career advancement and employee productivity. The results of the analysis are presented on Table 3.0.

in career advancement will lead to 0.501 increase in employee productivity and this is significant at 95% confidence level ($p < 0.05$). In order to take a decision on the hypothesis, the p-value of the estimated result is used. From the result, the P value obtained is (0.000) less than the conventional p-value (0.05) used in the study. This therefore implies that career advancement has a positive and significant effect on the employee productivity of selected hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Discussion of findings

The test of hypothesis revealed that career advancement had a significant effect on employee productivity of selected hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria. The findings of these study is consistent with Pillay, Dawood & Karodia (2015) in their study on relationship between career advancement on staff motivation, they found that career advancement had a positive correlation on motivation. Kaya and Ceylan (2014) carried out a study that a similar situation an empirical study on the role of career advancement programmes in organizations. Based on findings of the study and other studies before it, career advancement of an employee in the organization will lead to an increase in the productivity that employee will give back.

5. Conclusion and Recommendations

The study concluded that there was a statistically significant effect of career advancement on employees' productivity of selected Hotels in Lagos State, Nigeria.

Theoretically, the outcome of this study is in line with Equity theory. This is because equity theory advances the possibility of having a viable workforce based on equity and justice. Equity theory advances the reduced exploitation of workers, source of motivation and better interrelations among workers. This will ensure that the employees are remunerated and motivated adequately to improve and sustain overall productivity. Equity theory shows how fairly employees want to be treated and compensated for their contributions to the success of the organization. For the theory to be practicable, the assumptions which enable employees develop beliefs about what constitutes a fair and equitable compensation for the services they are rendering to the organisation should be in place. Furthermore, the assumption which employees have to make comparison with their peers in other organisations should also be in place. However, due to dynamism of the business environment, some of these assumptions are difficult to be practicalised.

In summarising the study recommendations, it is evident from the results of the study that organisations that encourages and motivate their employees regularly will most probably enjoy higher productivity. Furthermore, organised career advancement programmes in organisations tend to curb staff attrition rate because appropriate career advancement programmes tend to sustain hope of employees that they have brighter chances of climbing the corporate ladder if they work harder to sustain organisational productivity. Equally important is that organisations should institute robust staff training exercises where adequate knowledge and skills would be acquired that would be subsequently put to organisational productivity. Furthermore, organisation management should improve on providing conducive working environment that will enable the employees to put in their best at all times.

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